

On the Feasibility of Transformer-Based 3D Instance Segmentation for Underwater LiDAR Data

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Abstract—Underwater situational awareness is a critical component of maritime security, enabling inspection of submerged infrastructure, detection of hazardous objects, and monitoring of port and offshore environments. Traditional acoustic sensing methods, while robust over long distances, often suffer from limited spatial resolution, restricting their ability to detect small objects. Recent advances in underwater laser scanning can provide high-resolution 3D point clouds that enable detailed geometric reconstruction of submerged scenes. However, automated interpretation of such data remains challenging due to noise, scattering effects, and object occlusions.

In this work, we investigate the use of transformer-based 3D instance segmentation techniques for underwater laser-derived point clouds. We present a deep learning based pipeline that processes raw underwater point clouds and performs instance segmentation. Experimental evaluation of our datasets and our results highlight the potential of combining underwater laser scanning with advanced deep learning algorithms to improve maritime security applications such as infrastructure inspection, threat detection, and environmental monitoring.

Index Terms—Underwater Laser Scanning, Underwater Point Clouds, 3D Instance Segmentation, 3D Point Cloud Segmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime security operations rely on accurate and reliable perception of submerged environments for tasks such as infrastructure inspection, threat detection, and environmental monitoring. These applications require not only large-area coverage but also the ability to detect small objects and fine structural details. Traditional sensing modalities such as sonar and acoustic imaging provide robust long-range perception [1]–[3], but their limited spatial resolution restricts their effectiveness for fine-grained inspection tasks.

Recent advances in underwater laser scanning have introduced a promising alternative by enabling the acquisition of high-resolution 3D point clouds of submerged scenes [4], [5]. Compared to acoustic sensing, laser-based systems can capture dense geometric detail, potentially enabling object-level understanding and precise inspection.

In parallel, deep learning methods—particularly transformer-based architectures—have achieved strong performance in 3D instance segmentation for structured indoor and terrestrial environments. These methods rely on relatively clean, dense, and well-structured point clouds, and their ability to generalize to degraded sensing conditions

remains largely unexplored. In particular, it is unclear whether such approaches can operate reliably on underwater laser-derived point clouds, where noise, sparsity, and occlusions fundamentally alter the data distribution.

This gap raises a critical question: Can modern 3D instance segmentation methods effectively operate on underwater LiDAR data, and what adaptations are required to make them viable in this domain?

In this work, we address this question in the context of the UnderSec project by developing and evaluating an end-to-end pipeline for underwater scene understanding using laser-derived point clouds and transformer-based instance segmentation models. Rather than proposing a new model architecture, our focus is on systematically investigating the challenges posed by underwater data and identifying practical solutions.

Our contributions are as follows:

- We present one of the first evaluations of transformer-based 3D instance segmentation methods on underwater laser-derived point clouds.
- We develop a complete processing pipeline, including data acquisition, annotation, and model training, for underwater environments.
- We identify object sparsity as a critical bottleneck and propose a geometry-aware augmentation strategy to mitigate it.
- We provide empirical insights into the behavior and limitations of modern 3D segmentation models under underwater sensing conditions

Our results demonstrate that, despite significant noise and data degradation, transformer-based methods show promising performance, while also highlighting key challenges that must be addressed for reliable deployment in maritime security applications.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Underwater Laser Scanning

Underwater laser scanning and LiDAR sensing have emerged as high-resolution alternatives to traditional acoustic sensing for reconstructing submerged environments [4]–[6]. Existing works primarily focus on sensor design, calibration, and geometric reconstruction, demonstrating the ability of laser-based systems to capture fine structural details that are not accessible with sonar-based approaches.

Fig. 1. Illustration of underwater LiDAR [7] mounted on the side arm in the round basin. The sensor is marked with red arrows.

Depending on the sensing principle, such as Time-of-Flight or triangulation, these systems offer varying trade-offs between range, accuracy, and robustness to turbidity [7]–[9]. Applications include bathymetry, infrastructure inspection, and multi-modal reconstruction pipelines that combine optical and acoustic data [4], [5], [10], [11].

However, the majority of prior work is centered on data acquisition and reconstruction, with relatively limited attention to object-level scene understanding. In particular, automated interpretation of underwater LiDAR data remains underexplored, especially in the context of learning-based approaches that can operate directly on raw point clouds. This gap is critical because high-resolution geometry alone is insufficient for many maritime security applications that require the identification, separation, and analysis of individual objects within complex scenes.

B. 3D Instance Segmentation with Transformers

3D instance segmentation is a fundamental problem in 3D computer vision, aiming to simultaneously assign semantic labels and distinguish individual object instances within a scene. Recent progress has been driven by large-scale indoor datasets such as ScanNet and S3DIS [12], [13], which provide dense and well-annotated point clouds.

Early approaches relied on clustering, proposal generation, or hand-crafted geometric features. More recently, deep learning methods based on sparse convolutions and transformer architectures have significantly improved performance by enabling end-to-end learning and modeling of long-range spatial relationships. Transformer-based models such as OneFormer3D and Mask3D [14], [15] formulate instance segmentation as a set prediction problem, where a fixed number of queries are used to predict object masks. These approaches have demonstrated strong performance in structured environments with relatively clean and dense point clouds.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our goal is to evaluate the feasibility of applying modern transformer-based 3D instance segmentation methods to underwater LiDAR point clouds. A central challenge in this setting is that underwater data significantly deviates from the assumptions of standard 3D vision pipelines: it is noisy, incomplete, and contains very few object instances per scene.

Fig. 2. Illustration of annotations from CloudCompare [16]. The segmentation tool was used to segment objects of interest.

To address these challenges, we design a pipeline that not only processes underwater LiDAR data, but also explicitly tackles data sparsity through targeted augmentation. The pipeline consists of three main stages: (i) data acquisition and preprocessing, (ii) annotation, and (iii) model training with sparsity-aware augmentation.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

To capture representative underwater data, we performed controlled experiments in an indoor test basin at the Chair of Ocean Engineering, University of Rostock. A LiDAR sensor was mounted on a rotating arm, enabling both static and dynamic scanning configurations. The raw sensor data is processed using a trajectory estimation pipeline that integrates IMU and, when available, GNSS measurements. This step is essential for reconstructing a consistent global point cloud from temporally acquired scans. Each point is transformed into a common coordinate frame based on estimated sensor poses, resulting in a unified 3D representation of the scene.

TABLE I

EXTENT COLUMNS ARE THE MEAN (\pm STANDARD DEVIATION IN METERS) OF SCENE SIZE IN RESPECTIVE DIMENSIONS. Z IS THE DEPTH AXIS.

Extent-X	Extent-Y	Extent-Z	AP	Training Scenes	Testing Scenes
2.65 ± 0.95	2.97 ± 0.99	2.67 ± 0.42	6.21	12	4

B. 3D Annotation

Accurate instance-level annotations are required to evaluate segmentation performance. We use CloudCompare [16] to manually segment objects of interest within the reconstructed point clouds, as illustrated in Fig. 2. These annotations serve as the basis for training and evaluation.

C. Model

We evaluated two state-of-the-art transformer-based instance segmentation models: OneFormer3D and Mask3D [14], [15]. Both follow a similar architecture consisting of: (i) a sparse 3D U-Net backbone for feature extraction, (ii) a query initialization module, and (iii) an instance decoder that predicts individual masks for objects of interest.

Given an input point cloud $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 4}$, where the first three entries are the xyz coordinates and the fourth is the intensity, we first voxelize it and then extract features using a backbone network. These features are then processed by a transformer decoder, which predicts a fixed set of instance masks. A key

Fig. 3. Illustration of a scene without synthetically added objects (a) and with synthetic objects in (b). The added objects are marked by arrows.

difference between the models lies in query initialization. OneFormer3D leverages superpoints or parametric queries, while Mask3D uses farthest point sampling (FPS). This distinction becomes particularly relevant in sparse underwater scenes, where the number and distribution of objects are highly limited. During training, the predicted instance masks are matched to the ground-truth instances using Hungarian matching [14], [15], [17], [18]. The matching cost combines mask similarity and classification terms. Losses are computed over the matched pairs and applied at each decoder layer. We refer the reader to these works [14], [15] for further details.

D. Addressing Object Sparsity via Augmentation

A major limitation of our dataset is the extremely low frequency of objects of interest, typically only one or two instances per scene. This sparsity leads to unstable training and poor generalization, as the model receives insufficient supervision for learning object-level representations. To address this, we introduce a geometry-aware data augmentation strategy that increases object diversity while preserving physical realism. Instead of duplicating existing instances, we take an approach similar to [19], where ground truth (GT) objects are inserted into the scene. We insert synthetic objects derived from CAD models into real scenes. To ensure realistic placement, we first estimate a dominant support surface using RANSAC. Synthetic objects are then:

- Randomly scaled and sampled to simulate partial observations.
- Aligned with the support surface using ICP.
- Inserted only if they do not intersect with existing geometry.

This approach allows us to mimic the placement of objects in the real-world, such as objects attached to ship hulls or resting on harbor floors. An illustration is provided in Fig. 3 and the algorithm is briefly described in Algorithm 1

IV. EXPERIMENTS

We used MMDetection3D [21] for our experiments and official implementations of OneFormer3D and Mask3D. For OneFormer3D we use both variants, that is, with parametric

Algorithm 1 Scene augmentation by procedural object insertion

Input: Scene point cloud P , semantic and instance masks S, I , object set \mathcal{O} , maximum number of objects to insert n
Output: Augmented scene \hat{P} , and masks \hat{S}, \hat{I}
 Extract dominant plane $P_{support}$ using RANSAC [20]
 $\hat{P} \leftarrow P, \hat{S} \leftarrow S, \hat{I} \leftarrow I$
 $k \leftarrow \max(I)$
for $i = 1$ to n **do**
 Randomly select and scale object $O \in \mathcal{O}$
 Compute bounding cuboid of O
 Locate sufficient free cuboid region on $P_{support}$
 Align object base to support surface using ICP
 if no intersection with existing instances **then**
 Insert object points into \hat{P}
 Assign semantic label and instance ID $k + 1$
 $k \leftarrow k + 1$
 end if
end for
return $\hat{P}, \hat{S}, \hat{I}$

Fig. 4. Qualitative results from Oneformer3D-P. GT on left and model predictions on the right.

queries and with superpoints, referred to as OneFormer3D-P and OneFormer3D respectively. Starting the training from scratch, we applied random BEV flipping, global rotation, and scaling augmentations. Train/test splits and scene sizes are provided in Table I. During training, we randomly sampled $N = 10^6$ and set the voxel size at 1 centimeters (cm). All models were trained with a learning rate of 0.0001, batch size of 4 with the Adam optimizer [22] and cosine learning rate schedule [23] for 100 epochs. The Average Precision (AP) metrics are reported in Table II. Fig. 4 shows qualitative comparison between ground truth and model predictions.

TABLE II
 AVERAGE PRECISION (AP) VALUES COMPUTED AT VARIOUS THRESHOLDS
 ALONG WITH MEAN PRECISION AND RECALL AT IOU OF 50%

Model	AP ₂₅	AP ₅₀	AP	Prec ₅₀	Rec ₅₀
Oneformer3D	42.36	18.21	6.21	40.75	32.92
Oneformer3D-P	55.19	28.24	10.80	61.11	55.24
Mask3D	35.20	20.67	17.91	51.32	38.45

V. DISCUSSION AND KEY INSIGHTS

We now discuss key observations from our experiments, focusing on the behavior of transformer-based instance segmentation models under underwater sensing conditions.

A. Feasibility of Transformer-Based Methods Underwater

Our results indicate that transformer-based instance segmentation models, originally designed for structured indoor environments, remain partially effective on underwater LiDAR data. Despite significant noise, missing regions, and geometric distortions, the models are able to identify object instances with reasonable precision. However, the models are not inherently robust to underwater artifacts and data scarcity. They require adaptation for reliable deployment.

B. Impact of Object Sparsity

A key challenge in our dataset is the extremely low number of object instances per scene. It is hard in general to acquire the necessary broad range of underwater scenes/scans with objects of interest. This sparsity significantly affects the training stability and leads to reduced recall, as the model struggles to learn diverse object representations and fails to generalize to new scenes.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we investigated the feasibility of applying transformer-based 3D instance segmentation methods to underwater laser-derived point clouds in the context of maritime security applications. Our study highlights that, while modern architectures developed for terrestrial environments can be transferred to underwater data, their performance is significantly affected by domain-specific challenges. Future work should focus on developing models that explicitly account for underwater noise characteristics, improving robustness to incomplete observations, and leveraging multi-modal sensing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The authors also thank the University of Rostock for allowing access to the water canals for experimentation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Huang, Y. Zhu, W. Xiong, and S. Zhang, "Lightweight learning-based sonar point cloud semantic segmentation for underwater bridge inspection," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 178, p. 106387, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2025.106387.
- [2] J. Yan, Y. Zhu, W. Xiong, C. S. Cai, and J. Zhang, "A sonar point cloud driven method for underwater steel structure defects inspection," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 325, p. 120770, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.oceaneng.2025.120770.
- [3] S. Ma, J. Wang, Y. Huang, M. Tan, J. Yu and Z. Wu, "Underwater 3-D Point Cloud Reconstruction of a Single Sonar Image Based on Pseudo Front View," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 74, pp. 1-13, 2025, Art no. 4513113, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2025.3595608.
- [4] Jung, Kyungmin, Thomas Hitchcox, and James Richard Forbes. "Performance evaluation of 3d keypoint detectors and descriptors on coloured point clouds in subsea environments." arXiv preprint arXiv:2209.12881 (2022).
- [5] D. Wang, S. Xing, Y. He, J. Yu, Q. Xu, and P. Li, "Evaluation of a new lightweight UAV-borne topo-bathymetric LiDAR for shallow water bathymetry and object detection," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 4, p. 1379, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22041379.
- [6] K. Himri, P. Ridao, and N. Gracias, "Underwater object recognition using point-features, Bayesian estimation and semantic information," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 5, p. 1807, 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21051807.
- [7] Fraunhofer IPM, Underwater LiDAR (ULi): Optical 3D inspection of underwater infrastructure, Fraunhofer Institute for Physical Measurement Techniques IPM, Freiburg, Germany, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ipm.fraunhofer.de/content/dam/ipm/en/PDFs/product-information/OF/AUS/Underwater-LiDAR-ULi.pdf>. [Accessed: Mar. 8, 2025].
- [8] Kraken Robotics, "Subsea LiDAR services for precision," Kraken Robotics, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.krakenrobotics.com/services/lidar-solutions/>. [Accessed: Mar. 8, 2025].
- [9] Voyis Vision Ltd., Insight laser scanners – high-resolution underwater laser scanning solutions, Voyis, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://voyis.com/insight-laser-scanners/>. [Accessed: Mar. 8, 2025].
- [10] A. Smith, J. Coffelt and K. Lingemann, "A Deep Learning Framework for Semantic Segmentation of Underwater Environments," *OCEANS 2022*, Hampton Roads, Hampton Roads, VA, USA, 2022, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/OCEANS47191.2022.9977212.
- [11] X. Chu, H. Chen, D. Zou, J. Tian, Q. Gao, S. Zhou, Y. Liu, J. Wang, J. Zhou, X. Fu, and S. Liu, "A multimodal optical dataset for underwater image enhancement, detection, segmentation, and reconstruction," *Scientific Data*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 1554, Sep. 2025, doi: 10.1038/s41597-025-05797-w.
- [12] I. Armeni, O. Sener, A. Zamir, H. Jiang, I. Brilakis, M. Fischer, and S. Savarese, "3D semantic parsing of large-scale indoor spaces," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2016, pp. 1534–1543, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2016.170.
- [13] A. Dai, A. X. Chang, M. Savva, M. Halber, T. Funkhouser, and M. Nießner, "ScanNet: Richly-annotated 3D reconstructions of indoor scenes," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, 2017, pp. 5828–5839.
- [14] M. Kolodiazhyi, A. Vorontsova, A. Konushin, and D. Rukhovich, "OneFormer3D: One transformer for unified point cloud segmentation," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, 2024, pp. 20943–20953.
- [15] Schult, Jonas, Francis Engelmann, Alexander Hermans, Or Litany, Siyu Tang and Bastian Leibe. "Mask3D: Mask Transformer for 3D Semantic Instance Segmentation." 2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA) (2022): 8216-8223.
- [16] D. Girardeau-Montaut, CloudCompare, EDF RD and Telecom Paris-Tech, France, 2016.
- [17] J. Lu, J. Deng, C. Wang, J. He and T. Zhang, "Query Refinement Transformer for 3D Instance Segmentation," 2023 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), Paris, France, 2023, pp. 18470-18480, doi: 10.1109/ICCV51070.2023.01697.
- [18] H. W. Kuhn, "The Hungarian method for the assignment problem," *Naval Research Logistics Quarterly*, vol. 2, no. 1–2, pp. 83–97, 1955, doi: 10.1002/nav.3800020109.
- [19] Y. Yan, Y. Mao, and B. Li, "SECOND: Sparsely embedded convolutional detection," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 10, p. 3337, 2018, doi: 10.3390/s18103337.
- [20] M. A. Fischler and R. C. Bolles, "Random sample consensus: A paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 381–395, Jun. 1981, doi: 10.1145/358669.358692.
- [21] MMDetection3D Contributors, "MMDetection3D: OpenMMLab next-generation platform for general 3D object detection," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/open-mmlab/mmdetection3d>.
- [22] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba, "Adam: A method for stochastic optimization," arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980, 2014.
- [23] I. Loshchilov and F. Hutter, "SGDR: Stochastic gradient descent with warm restarts," arXiv preprint arXiv:1608.03983, 2016.